

An anankastic account of bare nouns in German

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Abstract

This paper investigates Article Drop (AD) with singular count nouns in spoken Standard German, presenting novel data on tool-denoting nouns. Although such nouns are typically resistant to AD, we show that AD can naturally occur when they appear in topical position and denote the inherently unique means to achieve a backgrounded goal. This constitutes a systematic exception to an otherwise robust ban on AD, explained by the fact that these bare nouns refer to objects that are uniquely identifiable in the stereotypical task-completing situations to which they are relativized. We thus propose an anankastic-like analysis, in which a (silent) teleological modal restricts the evaluation of the tool-denoting noun to situations where a given task is stereotypically completed using that tool. The paper further contributes to the theoretical landscape by exploring cross-linguistic extensions to languages such as Czech and Akan, offering preliminary support for a revised notion of weak definiteness grounded in inherent uniqueness. Finally, we highlight how modal operators and situation variables can restrict the reference of noun phrases even in the absence of overt determiners.

1. Introduction

Singular count nouns (SCNs) in German usually require an article (cf. Duden 2022: 263, normative rule 263). Escaping this generalization are cases that include predicative uses (see (1)),¹ coordinated NPs (cf. Heycock and Kroch (2002)) as in (2), NP-complements of prepositions *mit* and *ohne* (cf. Kiss 2019, 2010) as in (3), and NP-participants of short event descriptions as in (4). The latter are generally found in abbreviated registers like headlines (Lemke et al., 2017), user manuals, recipe instructions, text messages, note-taking, etc.²

(1) *Predicative NPs*

¹We employ the following glossing abbreviations: 1/2/3=first/second/third person, ACC/DAT/GEN/LOC/NOM=accusative/dative/genitive/locative/nominative case, AUX=auxiliary, COMP=complementizer, COP=copula, DEF=definite determiner, DEM=demonstrative, FUT=future, IMP=imperative, INDF=indefinite determiner, NEG=negation, PST=past tense, PCL=particle, PL=plural number, PRS=present/non-past tense, REL=relative pronoun, RP=resumptive pronoun, SG=singular number, SNG=strong article, WK=weak article.

²Wiese 2012 reports instances of P+D drop with verbs of movement in Kiezdeutsch and other varieties of German (see also Duden 2022: 196, normative rule 267). Similar observations have been made for London English in Hall 2019.

- a. Chester Bennington war **Sänger** von der Band “Linkin Park”.
 Chester Bennington was singer of DEF.DAT band Linkin Park
 ‘Chester Bennington was the lead singer of the band Linkin Park’
- (2) *Coordination*
- a. Vergiss nicht, **Eimer und Schaufel** mit an den Strand zu nehmen.
 forget NEG bucket and shovel with to DET.ACC beach to bring
 ‘Don’t forget to bring your bucket and shovel to the beach.’
- (3) *Within PPs*
- a. Wo kann man nur **mit Karte** zahlen?
 Where can one only with card pay
 ‘Where can I pay by card only?’
- b. Ich habe ein Haus **mit/ohne Wintergarten** gekauft.
 I have INDF house with/out wintergarten bought
 ‘I bought a house with/out winter garden.’
- (4) *Short event descriptions*
- a. **Schlange** beißt **Löwe**.
 snake bites lion

While productive in abbreviated registers, the omission of the article before SCNs in argument position is severely restricted in standard German. Recent work, however, has revealed that conditions licensing AD in subject SCNs are relaxed in specificational copular clauses (Geist, 2021), as illustrated in (5).

- (5) Vater des Babys ist der [...] Schauspieler Pete Dwojak.
 father DEF.GEN baby is DEF.NOM actor Pete Dwojak
 ‘The father of the baby is the actor Pete Dwojak.’ (from Geist 2021: 2, ex. 5)

However, outside of copular clauses, SCNs appear to be AD-resistant, as illustrated below.

- (6) Die Katze sprang weg, als *(der) Besen auf den Boden
 DEF.NOM cat jump.PST away when DEF.NOM broom on DEF.ACC floor
 fiel.
 fall.PST
 ‘The cat darted away when the broom fell to the floor.’

Contrary to common belief, some AD-instances with SCNs can indeed be found in spoken standard German. These occurrences have not been previously discussed and arise naturally in goal-oriented contexts as the one in (7), where the bare noun represents the means to a salient goal in discourse.

- (7) Context: *Du musst noch den Garten umgraben.* (‘you still have to dig up the garden.’)
- a. Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
 shovel stands in.DEF.DAT shed
 ‘A/the shovel is in the shed.’

Another example is illustrated by the comic strip in Fig. 1.³

Figure 1: Image sourced from <https://debeste.de/431894/>.

Similar constructions are easily found through corpus searches. Below are two examples.⁴

- (8) Oh prima kannst ja zum Treffen fliegen, **Besen** steht bereit.
 oh great can.2SG PCL to.DEF.DAT meeting fly broom stand ready
 ‘Oh great, you can fly to the meeting, the broom is ready.’
 (DeTenTen, token: 5559255662, source: <http://langhaarnetzwerk.de>)
- (9) Als Saisongast müssen Sie Selber regelmäßig rasenmähen [...]. **Rasenmäher**
 as season.guest must 3PL self regularly mow lawn mower
 steht bei der Rezeption zur Verfügung.
 is at DEF.DAT reception at.DEF.DAT disposal
 ‘As a seasonal guest you have to mow the lawn yourself regularly [...]. Lawn mower
 is available at the reception.’
 (DeTenTen, token: 20121234290, source: <https://www.hvidbjergstrand.de>).

In sentences (8)-(9), the bold-faced bare noun refers to the tool typically used to complete the task introduced in the preceding clause. For digging, said tool will be a shovel. For

³A: “May I court you, ma’am?” B: “Sure! The broom is in the shed, the lawnmower is in the garage!” The humor stems from the ambiguity of *den Hof machen*, which in its more literal (though unusual) sense means “to clean the courtyard.”

⁴All corpus data were accessed via Sketch Engine.

mowing, a lawnmower. Bare nouns such as *shovel* and *lawnmower*, which involve AD in goal-achieving contexts, will be referred to as “anankastic bare nouns” (ABNs).⁵ We refer to constructions depicting goal-achieving scenarios as “shovel sentences”. The clause that features an ABN will be called the tool-clause, while the clause backgrounding the relevant goal or task will be referred to as the goal- or antecedent-clause.

1.1. Desiderata, preview and structure of the paper

The goal of this paper is threefold:

- (i) To determine the conditions under which article drop occurs.
- (ii) To identify the semantic properties of ABNs, particularly in relation to (in)definiteness and discourse transparency.
- (iii) To develop a compositional and discourse model based on the findings from (i) and (ii).

A key observation is that anankastic bare nouns are modalized - they are evaluated with respect to teleological situations in which a task or goal is stereotypically achieved using that tool. Additionally, topicality plays a crucial role in facilitating article drop. Specifically, the implicit Question under Discussion (QuD) structure bridges a discourse gap between the goal-clause and the tool-clause.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 examines the empirical distribution of anankastic bare nouns. Section 3 develops the theoretical proposal in three steps: first, it introduces the notion of inherent uniqueness, modeled after Šimík (2021); second, it builds on this concept to outline a modal-conditional analysis of shovel sentences, drawing an analogy with anankastic conditionals; finally, it proposes a QuD-based account to explain the discourse link between the tool-clause and the goal-clause. Section 4 addresses empirical puzzles and extends the proposal to plural bare nouns. Section 5 explores the broader theoretical implications, particularly regarding the weak-strong distinction (Schwarz, 2009), thereby expanding the analysis beyond German. Finally, section 6 summarizes the findings and outlines directions for future research.

2. Empirical distribution

The data presented in this section were collected through acceptability judgment tasks with the assistance of six native consultants, following the methodology outlined in Matthewson (2004). Consultants were asked to assess the felicity of target sentences situated within a context.

2.1. The Data

In what follows, we focus on six syntactic and semantic properties that seem to correlate with article drop in the case of anankastic bare nouns: teleological contexts, topicalization, (non-)unique identifiability, (no) anaphoric linking, discourse transparency and restrictive modification.

(i) *Teleological contexts*

⁵From Ancient Greek *anankastikós* (“to force”, “to compel”. On the model of anankastic modality (von Wright, 1963)).

As noted in Section 1, article drop appears to target NPs that occur in goal-oriented contexts, where they denote the means or tool typically involved in achieving a given goal or completing a task. We test this apparent restriction by evaluating tool sentences containing ABNs in teleological (i.e., contexts that introduce a purpose for the entity denoted by the ABN) versus non-teleological contexts.

- (10) **Teleological context:** *Du musst noch den Garten umgraben. Guck' mal im Keller...*
 ('You still need to dig up the garden. Check the basement...')
 a. (Die) Schaufel steht da.
 DEF.NOM shovel stand there
 lit. '(the) shovel is there.'
- (11) **Non-teleological context:** *Gestern haben Diebe meinen Keller ausgeräumt, aber...*
 ('yesterday the thieves emptied my basement but...')
 a. #(Die) Schaufel steht (noch) da.
 DEF.NOM shovel stand still there
 lit. '(the) shovel is (still) there.'

Comparing teleological to non-teleological contexts reveals a clear contrast regarding the anankastic noun *Schaufel* ("shovel"). While the article is optional when the digging task is contextually introduced (as in (10)), omission is not allowed when the context does not establish a salient goal for the tool (as in (11)). Similarly for the noun *Besen* ("broom") below, AD is licensed only following a teleological context such as (12), while the article becomes obligatory if the surrounding context is non-teleological (see (13)).

- (12) **Teleological context:** *Du musst noch den Boden fegen.*
 ('You still need to sweep the floor.')
- a. (Der) Besen steht in der Abstellkammer.
 DEF.NOM broom stand in DEF.DAT storage.room
 lit. '(the) broom is in the storage room.'
- (13) **Non-teleological context:** *Gestern habe ich die Abstellkammer ausgemistet, und...*
 ('Yesterday, I cleared out the storage room, and...')
- a. #(Der) Besen steht (noch) da.
 DEF.NOM broom stand still there
 lit. '(the) broom is still there.'

It is important to stress that task-denoting contexts, such as the one in (12), are not inherently sufficient to license AD on anankastic NPs. In fact, a clear purpose-like relation between the given task and the item denoted by the ABN must be established. This is illustrated more clearly by the contrast in (14), where (14b) is causally linked to the antecedent clause, making it impossible for the NP *Vase* to appear bare.

- (14) Context: *Please clean up the floor and remove all the broken glass.*
- a. (Der) Besen steht im Keller.
 DEF.NOM broom stands in.DEF.DAT basement

- ‘The broom is in the basement.’
- b. #(Die) Vase ist aus dem Regal gefallen.
DEF.NOM vase AUX from DEF.DAT shelf fallen
 ‘The vase fell off the shelf.’

While the teleological constraint is strictly semantic, we will next show that ABNs are also restricted in terms of their syntactic position.

(ii) *Topicalization*

In most of the examples presented so far, ABNs consistently appear in the pre-field position. This structural restriction is not accidental and can be generalized, as demonstrated by the following minimal pairs.

- (15) Context: *Du musst noch den Garten umgraben.* (‘you still have to dig up the garden’)
 - a. Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
 shovel stand in.DEF.DAT shed
 - b. #Im Schuppen steht Schaufel.
 in.DEF.DAT shed stand shovel
 Intended: ‘A/the shovel is in the shed.’

(16) Context: *Vergiss nicht, den Boden zu fegen!* (‘Don’t forget to sweep the floor.’)

 - a. Besen steht im Keller.
 broom stand in.DEF.DATbasement
 - b. #Im Keller steht Besen.
 in.DEF.DATbasement stand broom
 Intended: ‘A/the broom is in the basement.’

In sentences (15)-(16), only variants with the ABN in the pre-field position are acceptable. When the count noun appears in the middle field - as in (15b)-(16b) - its determiner cannot be omitted. Importantly, this pattern is not restricted to subject NPs. As illustrated below, object NPs follow the same constraint.

- (17) Context: *Du musst noch den Garten umgraben.* (‘you still need to dig up the garden’)
 - a. Schaufel-Ø findest du im Schuppen.
 shovel-ACC find 2SG.NOM in.DEF.DAT shed
 - b. #Im Schuppen findest du Schaufel-Ø.
 in.DEF.DAT shed find 2SG.NOM shovel-ACC
 Intended: ‘You’ll find a/the shovel in the shed.’)

These empirical findings indicate that the observed restrictions are not due to a subject-object asymmetry but rather to the structural position of the NP. For now, we assume that the pre-field position of ABNs is a designated position for topicalized NPs – or, more generally, for left-peripheral topic NPs.

Having identified two key licensing conditions for AD, the next step is to assess the meaning components associated with ABNs, particularly in relation to categories such

as (in)definiteness and uniqueness. To this end, we examine whether ABNs denote situationally unique entities, establish anaphoric links, are discourse-transparent and permit non-restrictive modification.

(iii) Unique identifiability

Given the absence of an overt article, an obvious question is what meaning is associated with the anankastic bare noun. Based on the paraphrases adopted so far, the reader will have noticed that ABNs appear to be compatible with both definite and indefinite interpretations. This is confirmed by answers to questions inquiring about the cardinality of the ABN set, as illustrated in (18).

- (18) A: Ich brauche etwas, um mir Kommentare zu notieren. ('I need something to jot down comments.')
- a. B: Stift liegt in der Schublade.
pen lies in DEF.DAT drawer
'A/the pen is in the drawer.'
- b. Can the drawer contain more than one pen?
Consultants' judgment: Yes.

Similarly, for sentence (15) - repeated in (19), speakers observe that, the number of shovels in the shed is immaterial to the felicity of the sentence. What seems to be unique instead is the type of tool usually deployed for the depicted task.

- (19) Context: *Du musst noch den Garten umgraben.* ('you still have to dig up the garden')
- a. Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
shovel stand in.DEF.DAT shed
↪ there is at least one shovel in the shed.

While plausibility may still favor a definite interpretation in many of the cases under discussion, the number neutrality of ABNs is more convincingly demonstrated by examples such as (20):

- (20) Du musst das Bild noch aufhängen. Nagel ist in der
2SG.NOM must DEF.ACC picture still hang nail is in DEF.DAT
Werkzeugkiste.
toolbox.
'You still have to hang up the picture. A/the nail is in the toolbox.'
↪ there is at least one nail in the toolbox.

It is reasonable to assume that the toolbox might contain more than one nail. Yet, the sentence remains felicitous in this scenario.

(iv) Anaphoric linking

ABNs cannot be anaphorically linked to a salient antecedent, as shown in the following example.

- (21) Du musst noch den Garten umgraben. Darum habe ich **eine neue Schaufel** gekauft. ('You still need to dig up the garden. I've bought a new shovel for that.')
- a. #(Die) Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
 DEF.NOM shovel stands in.DEF.DAT shed

In (21a), the overt determiner *die* is required to refer back to the antecedent *eine Schaufel* in the preceding sentence.

(v) *Discourse transparency*

In keeping with discourse anaphora properties, although ABNs are not able to establish anaphoric relations with salient discourse antecedent, they can introduce referents themselves into the discourse. This point is illustrated by the following example.

- (22) Du musst immer noch den Rasen mähen. **Rasenmäher**₂ ist
 2SG.NOM must always still DEF.ACC lawn mow lawnmower is
 im Schuppen. Bitte stell **ihn**₂ zurück, wenn du fertig
 in.DEF.DAT shed please put 3SG.ACC back when 2SG.NOM finished
 bist.
 are
 'You still have to mow the lawn. The lawnmower is in the shed. Please put it
 back when you've finished.'

In (22), the pronoun *ihn* can pick up the co-indexed antecedent referent *Rasenmäher*. If ABNs were discourse opaque, then the use of an anaphoric pronoun in the subsequent discourse segment would be disallowed.

(vi) *Intersective modification*

Finally, some interesting constraints seem to arise with respect to predicates modifying anankastic bare nouns. Examples (23)-(25) show that sentences with ABNs become degraded when the bare noun is modified by an adjective.

- (23) Context: 'You still have to dig up the garden.'
 a. ??Rot-e Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
 red-NOM shovel stands in.DEF.DAT shed
 Intended: 'A/the new shovel is in the shed.'
- (24) Context: *Du musst noch dein Sandwich zubereiten.* ('You still have to make your sandwich.')
- a. ??Lecker-er Schinken steht im Kühlschrank.
 delicious-NOM ham stands in.DEF.DAT fridge.
 Intended: 'Some tasty ham is in the fridge.'
- (25) Context: *Vergiss nicht, das Auto zu washen.* ('Don't forget to wash the car.')
- a. ??Schön-en Eimer findest du im Keller.
 beautiful-ACC bucket find 2SG.NOM in.DEF.DAT basement
 Intended: 'You'll find a/the beautiful bucket in the basement.'

Similar results are obtained if the modifier is a PP or a relative clause, as illustrated below.

- (26) Context (24):
- a. ??Schinken von gestern steht im Kühlschrank.
 ham of yesterday stands in.DEF.DAT fridge.
 Intended: ‘The ham from yesterday is in the fridge.’
- b. ??Schinken, den Marie gekauft hat, steht im Kühlschrank.
 ham REL.ACC Marie bought stands in.DEF.DAT fridge.
 Intended: ‘The ham from yesterday is in the fridge.’

Despite a general aversion to intersective modification, ABNs seem to allow exceptions in certain cases. Specifically, ABNs admit restrictive modifiers that are necessary for the prototypical interpretation associated with the NP. Below are two examples:⁶

- (27) Context (24):
- a. Veganer Schinken steht im Kühlschrank.
 vegan.NOM ham stands in.DEF.DAT fridge
 Intended: ‘Some/the vegan ham is in the fridge.’
- (28) Context: *Du musst den Tisch lackieren.* (‘You have to varnish the table.’)
- a. Englischer Pinsel liegt im Malkasten.
 English.NOM brush lies in.DEF.DAT paintbox
 Intended: ‘An English brush is in the paint box.’

In sentences (27a)-(28a), a restrictive modifier is allowed, as it helps identify the specific type of ham/brush needed to achieve a particular goal. The use of these modifiers relies on certain auxiliary assumptions. For example, in context (27), the sandwich must be prepared for a vegan, so only a specific type of ham is appropriate. Similarly, in (28), the varnishing task is best completed with a particular kind of brush, namely an English paintbrush.

2.2. Interim summary: Distribution and special nature of ABNs

Table 1 summarizes the conditions that license ABNs and their resulting properties, comparing them to definite and indefinite DPs. Specifically, we illustrate the distribution of the three types of NP/DPs with respect to teleological contexts (Telos), topicalization (Topic), uniqueness, anaphoric linking, discourse (D) transparency and non-restrictive modification (NRM).⁷

⁶Note that forming prototypical NPs from modified ABNs is particularly challenging, as German typically favors compound nouns in such cases.

⁷Obligatory uses/properties are indicated by the symbol ‘✓’, ‘(✓)’ marks optionality, and ‘#’ denotes the absence of the property.

	Telos	Topic	Unique	Anaphoric	D-transparent	NRM
Anankastic bare noun	✓	✓	(✓)	#	✓	#
Definite DP	(✓)	(✓)	✓	✓	✓	(✓)
Indefinite DP	(✓)	(✓)	(✓)	#	✓	(✓)

Table 1: Distribution of ABNs compared to full definite and indefinite DPs in German

At first glance, Table 1 appears to show an overlap between ABNs and indefinite DPs, as both allow for non-unique interpretations and cannot be anaphorically linked to antecedent referents. However, ABNs are more restricted in their distribution, as they are only licensed when topicalized and in teleological contexts. Additionally, they entirely rule out non-restrictive modifiers.

The emerging picture sets ABNs apart from previously documented cases of article drop targeting singular count nouns, which were discussed in section 1. First, they differ from coordinated bare nouns, which strictly correlate with a uniqueness interpretation (Heycock and Kroch, 2002) (see (29)).

- (29) a. At the company meeting, president and vice-president gave an optimistic speech.
b. ??At the company meeting, employee and inspector talked about their colleagues' motivation.

In (29), only bare nouns referring to unique individuals (namely *president* and *vice-president*) may be coordinated. The sentence becomes degraded when the bare nouns denote non-unique individuals (*employee* and *inspector*). The uniqueness constraint on coordinated bare nouns contrasts with what is observed for ABNs, suggesting that the two constructions involve different meaning components.

Moreover, the fact that ABNs cannot be used anaphorically distinguishes them from strong definites (Schwarz, 2009), which are anaphoric in nature. More broadly, the lack of (strict) uniqueness and anaphoric properties indicates that ABNs do not fit neatly in Schwarz's weak-strong distinction. We return to this point in section 4.

Finally, we note that ABNs cannot be assimilated to (pseudo-)incorporated bare nouns (Farkas and de Swart, 2003; Dayal, 1999, 2011; Driemel, 2023). Although the two categories share key properties - most notably, number neutrality - they differ in discourse transparency. While incorporated bare nouns are typically discourse-opaque, we have seen that anankastic bare nouns can serve as antecedents to pronouns.

Having outlined the main properties and conditions that license the use of anankastic bare nouns, we now turn to a compositional analysis that accounts for the empirical observations discussed in this section.

3. The Proposal

This section proposes a formal account of the meaning associated with anankastic bare nouns and of their semantic composition with both goal and tool-clauses. Following the empirical distribution discussed in section 2, a successful theory should clarify the close

connection between ABNs and teleological contexts, as well as their restriction to topical positions.

3.1. Preview and theoretical framework

In a nutshell, ABNs denote entities that are inherently unique in some stereotypical goal-achieving situation identified by the antecedent-clause (cf. Šimík 2021). To compose with the tool-clause, they are ι -shifted, with uniqueness arising via a presupposition arising through a covert modal PP. At broader sentential level, we argue that shovel sentences involve modal structures akin to anankastic conditionals, whereby the covert modal quantifies over situations that are teleologically restricted to the agent’s goals (von Stechow and Iatridou, 2005; Condoravdi and Lauer, 2016). Finally, we show that topicalization is a crucial piece of the puzzle, as topicalized ABNs reveals the hidden discourse structure by providing the answer to a super-question under discussion (cf. Schwarz 2009).

The section is organized in three parts, reflecting the tripartite proposal. Before that, we first introduce the theoretical framework underlying our analysis. Subsection 3.2 builds on (Šimík, 2021)’s distinction between inherent and accidental uniqueness, demonstrating that ABNs pattern with the former. Based on this, inherent uniqueness is derived from the ordering source of a covert teleological modal within the bare NP. Subsection 3.3 extends the analysis, linking the structure and interpretation of shovel sentences to that of so-called anankastic conditionals, thereby offering a compositional analysis of the tool-clause. Finally, Subsection 3.4 integrates these components, proposing a model in which the tool-clause and goal-clause are connected via the question under discussion (QuD). Specifically, we suggest that the topicalized bare noun answers a silent super-question under discussion derived from the goal-clause, thereby explicating its relevance.

3.1.1. Theoretical assumptions

This work is situated within a modified version of a possibilistic situation semantics framework (Kratzer, 2019), where sentences are evaluated relative to a situation. For ease of exposition, we depart slightly from the standard Kratzerian framework and assume that situations are world-time pairs, thereby encompassing spatio-temporal coordinates (Keshet, 2008).⁸ Since Cresswell (1990), intensional operators such as modals and tenses have been shown to have the power of quantifying over situations (world and times) in the object language. Following recent conventions, we assume that situation variables are syntactically projected as phonologically null pronouns (Percus, 2000; Keshet, 2010; Schwarz, 2012), which are either freely assigned a value via the context-dependent function g (Heim and Kratzer, 1998) or bound by λ -abstractors that are freely inserted at LF.⁹

To illustrate, nouns such as *shovel* in the example below are of type $\langle s, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ and denote functions from situations to functions from entities to truth values.¹⁰

⁸In Kratzer’s system, situations are subparts or slices of worlds.

⁹This view is compatible with Bittner (1994); Kusumoto (1999); Keshet (2010), among others, but differs from that of Heim and Kratzer (1998), in which λ -abstraction is tied to movement.

¹⁰Where ‘ x ’ $\in D_e$, ‘ x ’ ranges over entities of type e ; ‘ s ’ $\in D_s$, ‘ s ’ ranges over situations of type s ; Truth-

$$(30) \quad \llbracket \text{shovel} \rrbracket^{g,c11} = \lambda s: s \in D_s. \lambda x: x \in D_e. \text{shovel}(s)(x) = 1 = x \text{ is a shovel in } s.^{12}$$

Regarding the expression of modality, we follow Kratzer (1991) in assuming that the meaning of a modal is determined by three parameters: *modal force* (existential or universal), a *modal base* (circumstantial or epistemic) and an *ordering source*, which orders the worlds of the modal base according to a given ideal (e.g., laws and norms for deontic modality, desires for bouletic modality, goals for teleological modality, etc.). To illustrate, we provide an example of a bouletic ordering source in (31), adapted from Hacquard (2006: 36) to fit our framework.¹³

$$(31) \quad \text{Bouletic ordering source } g_{Boul}: \\ \text{For all situations } s, s' \in \langle W, T \rangle: s <_{Boul} s' \text{ iff } \{p: p \in Boul \ \& \ s \in Boul\} \supset \{p: \\ p \in Boul \ \& \ s' \in Boul\}$$

The ordering source g_{Boul} imposes an ordering $<_{Boul}$ on the set $Boul$ (that is, the set of propositions satisfying the speaker's desires), such that the situations s are ranked higher than s' according to a bouletic ideal.¹⁴

Typically, modals select the highest-ranked situations (or worlds) based on the ordering imposed by an ordering source. To formalize this, we define a *MAX* function for a given ordering source g_{Ord} , as shown in (32).

$$(32) \quad \text{MAX}_{g_{Ord}} = \{s: s \in \langle W, T \rangle: \neg \exists s': s' \in \langle W, T \rangle. s' <_{Ord} s\}$$

Under a bouletic ordering source, the function *MAX* in (32) returns the highest-ranked situations according to the speaker's desires – that is, the situations that include most propositions compatible with the speaker's desires.

With these formal tools and theoretical assumptions in place, we now turn to our proposal.

3.2. Inherent uniqueness

We concluded section 2 noting that Schwarz (2009)'s weak/strong distinction does not equally extend to cases involving anankastic (bare) nouns. One more promising approach is offered in Šimík (2021), which distinguishes between inherently and accidentally unique NPs. More specifically, in Czech, while bare nouns denote entities that are assumed to be unique in typical situations resembling the topic one, NPs modified by a demonstrative pick out individuals that happen to be unique in the topic situation itself. The contrast is exemplified below (slightly adapted from Šimík 2021:367).

values, such as '1' (true) and '0' (false), are of type $t \rightarrow D_t = \{0,1\}$. If a and b are semantic types, then $\langle a,b \rangle$ is a semantic type. Nothing else is a semantic type.

¹¹Given a context c and an assignment function g , the interpretation function $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket^{g,c}$ takes a linguistic expression as input and returns its denotation (Heim and Kratzer, 1998: 15). For the remainder of the paper, we assume that all denotations are relativized to the parameters g and c , though these are omitted from the interpretation function for simplicity.

¹²For simplicity, we omit the domain of the function from the denotations in the rest of the paper.

¹³With $\langle W, T \rangle$ the world-time set-pair containing all the possible worlds, including the actual world, and all times, including the utterance time.

¹⁴That means that s will include more propositions satisfying the speaker's desires than s' . Thus, situations s represent best what the speaker's desire-situations should look like.

- (33) Situation s_1 : Teacher (T) with pupils in a classroom. T addresses one of the students:
 a. ‘Smaž (#tu) **tabuli**, prosím.’
 erase.IMP DEM blackboard please
 ‘Erase the blackboard, please.’
- (34) Situation s_2 : A and B are having a conversation, A is holding a book (the only book in the situation), B says (without any salient pointing gesture and without having talked about the book ever before):
 a. ‘{Dej / Ukaž} mi #(tu) knihu.’
 give.IMP show.IMP 1SG.ACC DEM book
 ‘Give/Show me the book.’

In example (33), the NP *tabuli* (‘blackboard’) is inherently unique and must therefore appear bare, as the context refers to classroom-like situations that typically involve a unique blackboard. By contrast, in (34), the NP *knihu* (‘book’) requires a demonstrative, since books are not inherently unique in contexts involving conversations between two people. In such situations, items like books can only be characterized as accidentally unique.

Setting aside accidental uniqueness, Šimík’s notion of inherent uniqueness is framed within a situation semantics framework (Kratzer, 2019) and formalized as in (35) (from Šimík 2021: 372).

- (35) For any property P , entity x and situation s_{top} , such that $P(s_0)(x) = 1$,
 x is **inherently uniquely identifiable** in s_0 iff $\forall s[s \approx s_0 \rightarrow \exists!y[P(s)(y)]]$
 All situations that are like s_{top} are such that there is exactly one entity with property P in those situations.

The accessibility relation \approx consists of two conversational backgrounds: a circumstantial modal base f and a stereotypical ordering source g . This way, all the situations s are restricted to the most “usual” ones among those that comply with facts and circumstances in the topic situation s_0 .¹⁵

Note that the inherent uniqueness of Czech bare nouns is a pragmatic presupposition and, therefore, is not contributed at the lexical-semantic level.¹⁶ In other words, while Czech bare NPs are presuppositionally relativized to stereotypical situations, their truth-conditional evaluation is anchored to the topic situation. At the level of assertion, Czech bare NPs denote entities, which are derived via a skolemized choice function. This function carries a situation index, takes the NP-property as input, and returns the unique entity in the indexed situation (for details, see Šimík 2021: 375).

Building on Šimík’s analysis, we argue that anankastic bare nouns denote inherently unique entities in stereotypical situations. However, we depart from his account in three key respects: (a) the presupposition of inherent uniqueness is not triggered pragmatically

¹⁵We do not report the extended formulation to avoid repetition, as a similar version is offered in (40). For the original formulation, we refer the reader to example (10) in Šimík (2021: 373).

¹⁶Šimík does not explicitly explain how this presupposition arises. He simply states that it is “part of our knowledge about topic situations” (Šimík, 2021: 375).

but is instead semantically encoded by a covert modal operator *FOR*; (b) the bare NP is not interpreted relative to the topic situation but rather to teleological situations accessible from the goal-clause; and (c) the property denoted by the bare noun undergoes ι -shifting, yielding an entity.

Returning to our paradigmatic example in (7) repeated in (36), we assume for the tool-clause the underlying simplified structure in (36b) (to be revised later), where the bare noun is modified by the silent *dafür* ('for that'), which undergoes covert movement to [spec,NP].

- (36) *Du musst noch den Garten umgraben. Schaufel steht im Schuppen.*
 a. Goal-clause: Du musst noch den Garten umgraben.
 b. Tool-clause: Schaufel dafür steht im Schuppen.
 $[_{TopP} s_0 [_{CP} [_{NP} [_{PP} da_7 FOR] [_{N'} Schaufel]] [_{VP} steht im Schuppen]]]$

Following Schwarz (2009: 95), we assume that topic situations are syntactically adjoined to the topmost node of the tree structure. The covert *dafür* is the spell-out of the teleological modal *FOR* and the situation proform *da*₇.¹⁷ The PP restricts the evaluation of the NP *Schaufel* to the situations quantified over by the modal. However, the ABN is not evaluated with respect to the topic situation s_0 but rather to the situation denoted by the goal-clause in (36a), which is accessed via the free pronoun *da*₇. The composition of the goal-clause is illustrated in (38). Here, the necessity modal *must* is assigned a Kratzer-style denotation, adapted to a possibilistic situation semantics framework, as shown in (37). The accessibility relation R^{Sp}_{Boul} is bouletic, meaning it selects situations that are compatible with the speaker's desires (with the indexical parameters *Sp* and *Ad* picking out the utterance's speaker and addressee, respectively).¹⁸

$$(37) \quad \llbracket \text{must} \rrbracket^{Sp,Ad}(s_0)(R^{Sp}_{Boul})(p) = \forall s[R^{Sp}_{Boul}(s_0)(s) \rightarrow p(s) = 1]$$

- (38) *Semantic composition of the goal-clause*:
 a. s^{topic} = gardening situation, with a father addressing his son:
Du musst noch den Garten umgraben. ('You still need to dig up the garden.')
- b. LF: $[must_{s_0, R_{Boul}} [du_4 [dig-up\ garden]]]$
 c. $\llbracket (38b) \rrbracket^{Sp,Ad} = 1$ iff $\forall s[R^{Sp}_{Boul}(g(0))(s) \rightarrow dig-up(s)(garden)(g(4))]$
 (with $g(4) = Ad$, $g(0) = s^{topic}$)
 d. *Paraphrase*: 'For all situations s , such that s is compatible with the speaker's desires in the topic situation s^{topic} , the addressee digs up the garden in s .'

The set of desire-situations satisfying the goal-proposition are accessed in the tool-clause through the situation pronoun *da*₇, as indicated below.

¹⁷For an analysis of *da* as a situation proform, see also Salfner and Salfner (2011).

¹⁸To maintain clarity of exposition, we approximate the accessibility relation of the auxiliary modal in the goal-clause as a bouletic modal base anchored to the speaker's desires. However, a more precise alternative is proposed by Ninan (2005), where *must*- p sentences exhibit imperative-like force, functioning as the speaker's attempt to have the addressee add p to their to-do list (cf. Hacquard 2006). We leave the potential integration of this approach into our proposal for future work, noting that it is particularly promising as it unifies the analysis of both imperative and *must* goal-clauses — both of which, as we have seen, productively license anankastic bare nouns.

$$(39) \quad \llbracket \text{da}_7 \rrbracket = g(7) = \{s: R^{Sp}_{Boul}(g(0))(s) \ \& \ \text{dig-up}(s)(\text{garden})(g(4))\}$$

As a second step, we incorporate inherent uniqueness into the teleological modal *FOR* as part of its presuppositional meaning. In line with Šimík, we assume that the situations quantified over are restricted by two conversational backgrounds: a circumstantial modal base f and a stereotypical ordering source g_{Norm} . These semantics will be revised later when *FOR*'s teleological component is factored in.

- (40) a. $[_{NP} [_{PP} \text{da}_7 [[\text{FOR } f] g_{Norm}]] [_{N'} \text{Tool}]]$
 b. *Presupposition of the teleological modal FOR* (to be revised)
 $\llbracket \text{FOR} \rrbracket(f)(g_{Norm})(\llbracket \text{da}_7 \rrbracket)(\llbracket [_{N'} \text{Tool}] \rrbracket)$ is defined iff
 $\forall s'[s' \in \text{MAX}_{g_{Norm}, g(7)}(\cap f(g(7))) \rightarrow \exists! y[\text{tool}(s')(y) = 1]]$
Paraphrase: ‘For all the best-ranked situations s' – ranked according to what is usually the case in $g(7)$ (i.e., in stereotypical goal-achieving situations) – among those compatible with the facts holding in $g(7)$, there exists a unique y such that y has the property P in s' .’
 c. *Truth-conditional contribution*
 When defined, $\llbracket \text{FOR} \rrbracket(f)(g_{Norm})(\llbracket \text{da}_7 \rrbracket)(\llbracket [_{N'} \text{Tool}] \rrbracket) = \lambda x.\text{tool}(s'[s' \in \text{MAX}_{g_{Norm}, g(7)}(\cap f(g(7)))](x))$

When applying to the property *shovel*, the modal *FOR* in (40) presupposes the existence of a unique entity that satisfies the property of being a shovel in all the best-ranked stereotypical situations where the addressee digs up the garden according to the speaker's desires. These situations are drawn from the set of situations that are compatible with the facts in such garden-digging situations. At the level of assertion, *FOR* merely returns the modalized tool-property.

While the computed definedness condition presents the entity denoted by the bare noun as inherently unique in the goal situation, its instrumental role in achieving the goal remains only implicit in (40b). The next subsection aims to spell out this functional relation in more explicit terms.

3.3. Anankastic modality

In this subsection, we demonstrate that the functional relation involved in shovel sentences is anankastic (von Wright, 1963; Sæbø, 2001). We justify this choice of modality by drawing an analogy between shovel sentences and two types of conditionals: anankastic conditionals (ACs) (Sæbø, 2001; von Fintel and Iatridou, 2005; Condoravdi and Lauer, 2016) and biscuit conditionals (BCs) (Goebel, 2020; Austin, 1956; Biezma and Goebel, 2018).

Shovel sentences share with these conditionals an anankastic structure, in which a goal antecedent is followed by information about the means to achieve it. Additionally, they give rise to inferences about how to accomplish the goal interpreted as advice or suggestions (see also Goebel 2020: 240-241). Below, we present two well-known examples of ACs and BCs.

- (41) a. If you want to go to Harlem, you should take the A train. (AC)
 b. If you are hungry, there are biscuits on the sideboard. (BC)

Here, we focus on the parallel between shovel sentences and anankastic conditionals, while we return to biscuit conditionals in subsection 3.4. For examples like (41a), Condoravdi and Lauer (2016) demonstrate that the consequent clause establishes a necessary condition for achieving the goal while also signaling the agent’s effective preference for the action taken to fulfill it. This is reflected in the implication in (41a) that taking the A train is the optimal way for the addressee to reach Harlem. These implications extend to shovel sentences, where, under certain circumstances, the use of a tool is perceived as a highly effective means of accomplishing the goal.

Building on these observations, we refine the semantics of the covert modal *FOR* in (40b), ensuring that its definedness condition applies specifically to situations where the goal is achieved in accordance with the agent’s effective preference. Following Condoravdi and Lauer (2016), we assume a historical modal base f_{Hist} and introduce a second ordering source g',Ad , which captures the agent’s effective preferences – in this case, those of the addressee (see the revised LF in (42)). The historical modal base f_{Hist} adds a restriction to the relevant situations, such that these include future continuations where the goal is accomplished (cf. Kaufmann and Schwager (2009)).¹⁹ Finally, the instrumental role played by the tool-denoting bare noun is made explicit by the function *Instrument*. This takes as arguments the entity denoted by the bare noun y and the teleological situation s , thus assigning an instrumental role to y in s . The amended presupposition is given in (43).

(42) *Revised LF for anankastic bare NPs*

(43) *Presupposition of the teleological modal FOR*

$$\llbracket \text{FOR} \rrbracket (f_{Hist})(g_{Norm})(g',Ad)(da_7)(P) \text{ is defined iff}$$

$$\forall s' [s' \in \text{MAX}_{g_{Norm}, g(\tau), g',Ad}(\cap f_{Hist}(g(\tau))) \rightarrow \exists! y [P(s')(y) = 1 \ \& \ \text{Instrument}(s')(y) = 1]]$$

Paraphrase: ‘Given the goal-situations $g(\tau)$ (i.e., situations compatible with the speaker’s desires, where the addressee’s goal is to dig up the garden), for all its most typical continuations s' that are ranked highest according to the addressee’s effective preferences and where the goal in $g(\tau)$ is eventually realized are such

¹⁹The use of a historical modal base rather than the circumstantial one in (40b) is intended to capture the temporal nature of the modal’s accessibility relation. For any world w and time t , a historical modal base partitions the set of accessible situations in w at t into those that are indistinguishable from w up to t . Historical alternatives, however, begin to diverge from t onward (cf. Kaufmann and Schwager 2009: 252). Accordingly, we interpret the situations constrained by f_{Hist} as future or possible continuations from t forward. The reference time t is determined by the clausal tense.

that there exists a unique y , such that y has the property P in s' and y has an instrumental role in s' ?

Through *FOR*'s presupposition in (43), we are able to tie the ABN's inherent uniqueness to anankastically modalized situations. At truth-conditional level, all *FOR* does is relativize the situations where the ABN is evaluated to teleological ones, leaving its semantic type unchanged.²⁰ As a result, the bare NP modified by *dafür* cannot compose with the rest of the clause, as it still denotes a property. To allow semantic composition, we assume that the bare NP is ultimately ι -shifted into an entity (see LF in (45)). In (46), we show how the analysis correctly derives the meaning of the tool-clause repeated in (44b) in italics, evaluated in the topic situation given in (44a).²¹

- (44) a. s^{topic} : father and son are standing in the yard. The father turns to his son and says:
 b. You still need to dig up the garden. *Schaufel <dafür> steht im Schuppen.* ('A/the shovel (for that) is in the shed.')

(45) *LF of the tool-clause in (44b):*

For the LF in (45), we assume that the subject NP is interpreted in situ in [spec,vP]. We revisit this choice in subsection 3.4.1, where we explore the possibility of the bare noun

²⁰This means that the existence of a unique entity in the *FOR*-situations is not asserted but simply presupposed. We return to this point later.

²¹In the current formalization, we omit the presupposition of existence and uniqueness typically associated with ι . This is done, first, to avoid redundancy, since these presuppositions are already introduced by *FOR*; and second, to prevent concerns about overgeneration. We return to this point in section 4. Alternatively, one could assume that the presuppositions arise only via ι , after the ABN has been modalized by *FOR*. The two approaches are compositionally equivalent.

being interpreted in a higher position.²² Crucially, the main predicate in the VP and the bare NP are evaluated with respect to different situations: while the VP is relativized to the topic situation (by having its situation variable s_0 bound by s^{topic}), the situation pronoun of the bare noun *Schaufel* (that is s_2) is locally bound by the teleological modal *FOR* through a co-indexed abstractor. This is reflected in the meaning derived in (46), where for readability we include the domain restriction of the universal quantifier *FOR* only in the definedness condition.²³

(46) *Semantic composition of (45):*

- a. *Definedness conditions:* $\llbracket (45) \rrbracket$ is defined iff
 $\llbracket \text{FOR} \rrbracket(\text{f}_{Hist})(\text{g}_{Norm})(\text{g}^{Ad})(\text{da}_7)(\lambda s''. \llbracket \text{Schaufel} \rrbracket)$ is defined iff
 $\forall s'[s' \in \text{MAX}_{\text{g}_{Norm}, \text{g}(7), \text{g}^{Ad}}(\cap \text{f}_{Hist}(\text{g}(7))) \rightarrow \exists! y[\text{shovel}(s')(y) = 1 \ \& \ \text{Instrument}(s')(y) = 1]$
Paraphrase: ‘For all the most typical situations s' compatible with situations depicted in $\text{g}(7)$ (i.e., situations where the addressee digs up the garden in s^{topic} according to the speaker’s desires) and that are the closest fit to the addressee’s epistemic preferences, such that all their future continuations where the garden is eventually dug up are such that there exists a unique y , such that y is a shovel in s' and y has an instrumental role in s' .’
- b. *Truth-conditions:* If defined, $\llbracket (45) \rrbracket = 1$ iff
 $\text{in}(s^{topic})(\text{shed})(\iota x[\forall s'[\dots] \ \& \ \text{shovel}(s')(x)])$
Simplified paraphrase: ‘The x , that is typically utilized in digging-situations and that is a shovel in those situations, is located in the shed in the topic situation.’

As the paraphrase in (46a) illustrates, the property of ‘shovelness’ is evaluated with respect to stereotypical garden-digging situations—further restricted to continuations where the goal is achieved according to the addressee’s preferences—rather than the actual topic situation (i.e., the yard situation depicted in (44a)). This aligns well with our empirical observations. Recall that, according to our consultants, the anankastic bare noun in shovel sentences refers to the item typically used in situations similar to the topic situation, rather than a specific entity present in the situation under discussion.

Furthermore, we have shown that ABNs exhibit number neutrality and do not require the existence of a unique individual in the topic situation. For instance, native speakers

²²We take no stance on whether ABNs syntactically project full DPs (with a phonologically null determiner corresponding to ι) or NPs. Some support for a DP-analysis comes from the adjective-noun agreement patterns observed with restrictive modifiers in (63)-(64), in which the D-head, if structurally present, would require a gender-invariant morpheme *-e* for the adjective (e.g., $\langle \text{der} \rangle$ *veganE Schinken*, $\langle \text{der} \rangle$ *EnglischE Pinsel*) (cf. Lipták and Sybesma (2024) on Dutch and German headlines). However, the D-analysis is challenged by vocative NPs, which despite being articleless follow the bare noun paradigm (e.g., *liebER Präsident* ‘dear president’, *oh, du armES Ding!* ‘oh, you poor thing!’). This suggests a phonological rather than syntactic motivation behind these agreement patterns (many thanks to Roberto Zamparelli for bringing this to our attention).

²³For simplicity, we assume that the present tense is semantically vacuous (Sauerland, 2002). Given that situations can have a temporal dimension (cf. Schwarz 2009: 84), one could alternatively adopt a relative semantics for the present tense, where the reference situation/time is equated with the local situation/time of evaluation (in this case, the topic situation). The outcome remains the same.

have pointed out that sentences like (44b) can be felicitously uttered even in contexts where multiple shovels are stored in the shed. This follows naturally from our analysis, as the presupposition of uniqueness is tied not to the topic situation itself but to typical situations in which the activity designated by the topic situation is successfully completed. In this respect, an informal paraphrase of (44b) consistent with the truth conditions in (46b) would be: ‘The shovel that you need for that is in the shed.’²⁴

To conclude this subsection, the modal analysis we have proposed explains the intimate link between anankastic bare nouns and teleological scenarios. Since inherent uniqueness emerges as part of the functional relation between the bare noun and the goal-clause, it becomes clear why the omission of the article is exceptionally allowed in these contexts. However, our empirical investigation reveals that teleological contexts alone are not a sufficient condition-anankastic NPs can appear bare only when they occur in sentence-initial position. The next subsection addresses this restriction in detail.

3.4. Topicality and the QuD-based discourse model

So far we have developed an analysis of anankastic bare nouns (and more broadly of shovel sentences) that does not account for their structurally high position. In what follows, we show that anankastic bare NPs are interpreted in [spec,CP] as topics of the tool-clause. In particular, in line with Roberts (2011), we take discourse topics to denote questions under discussion. More specifically, the topicalized ABN is the answer to an implicit super-question under discussion, thus bridging a “discourse gap” between the goal-clause and the tool-clause.

We start by noting that discourse models relying on the question under discussion have been successfully applied to constructions similar to shovel sentences, such as biscuit conditionals (Biezma and Goebel, 2018; Goebel, 2020). As discussed in subsection 3.3, biscuit conditionals (also known as relevance conditionals) and shovel sentences exhibit striking similarities, with both the consequent of a biscuit conditional and the tool-clause appearing to offer a recommendation or advice.

- (47) a. Du musst noch den Garten umgraben. Schaufel steht im Schuppen. (‘You still need to dig up the garden. A/the Shovel is in the shed.’)
 b. If you are hungry, there are biscuits on the sideboard.

Both shovel sentences and biscuit conditionals depict the **means to achieve a certain goal** (*dig up a garden* in (47a), *sate hunger* in (47b)). Additionally, in both constructions the truth of the tool-clause/consequent is not entailed by the truth of the antecedent-clause (cf. Austin 1956; Biezma and Goebel 2018; Goebel 2020 for BCs): the shovel (just like the biscuits) is found in the shed (on the sideboard) regardless of whether the garden is being dug up (the addressee is hungry).

(48) *Lack of conditional entailment*

²⁴The analysis we propose receives additional support from standard tests of presupposition. Consider (i):

(i) Schaufel steht nicht im Schuppen. (‘A/the shovel is not in the shed.’)

In (i), the existence of a unique shovel typically used for digging tasks cannot be challenged by negation, indicating that this condition is presuppositionally encoded.

- a. The addressee must dig up the garden \rightarrow the shovel is in the shed.
- b. The addressee is hungry \rightarrow the biscuits on the sideboard.

Moreover, shovel sentences share some of the inferences arising with BCs. For example, it has been argued that BCs like (47b) trigger a *permission* inference, whereby the speaker grants the addressee permission regarding the content of the consequent (Biezma and Goebel, 2018; Goebel, 2020). Similarly, shovel sentences carry the tacit inference that the addressee is allowed to make use of the tool to achieve the specified goal. This is illustrated in (49).

(49) *Permission inference*

- a. If you are hungry, there are biscuits on the sideboard.
 \rightsquigarrow You're allowed to eat the biscuits.
- b. Du musst noch den Garten umgraben. Schaufel ist im Schuppen.
 \rightsquigarrow You are allowed to use the shovel.

If the two constructions share the same underlying semantics and pragmatics, we should expect that when shovel sentences take the form of biscuit conditionals, they should likewise license the omission of the article for the tool-denoting noun. This prediction is strikingly confirmed, as illustrated by the following example:

- (50) a. Wenn du den Garten umgraben musst/möchtest, Schaufel
 if 2SG.NOM DEF.ACC garden dig.up must/would.like shovel
 steht im Schuppen.
 stands in.DEF.DAT shed
- b. Schaufel steht im Schuppen, wenn du umgraben musst/möchtest.
 'If you need/want to dig up the garden, there's a shovel in the shed.'

The “shovel conditional” in (50) closely aligns in meaning and pragmatic inferences with the canonical shovel sentences discussed so far. Notably, the anankastic bare noun can feature in a pre-verbal position even when the pre-field hosts the if-clause (as in (50a)). This is particularly telling, as V2 word order in the consequent of a German conditional has been used as a diagnostic for a biscuit reading of the conditional (as opposed to a standard indicative conditional reading; see Ebert et al. (2014: 360)).

Building on Goebel's analysis of BCs, we argue that the integration of the tool-clause with the goal-clause, along with the associated pragmatic inferences, is best understood within a discourse model based on the notion of the Question under Discussion (QuD) (Roberts, 1996; Büring, 2003).

Following this model, discourse is conceptualized as a sequence of moves, where assertions serve as answers to an implicit or explicit question that sets the stage for the interaction. This discourse model draws from Carlson et al. (2006)'s view of dialogue as a dynamic exchange, with each statement contributing to the resolution of the ongoing Question Under Discussion. In this framework, implicit questions must be identifiable through linguistic or grammatical cues.

Roberts discusses prosody as one strategy for making such non-overt questions identifiable. We propose that topicalization serves as another strategy employed by interlocutors

to signal and retrieve an implicit QuD. In this way, the topicalized bare noun “shovel” in (47a) answers the implicit question “What do I need for that?”, which directly follows from the goal-clause.

Guiding discourse participants through the sequence of moves is the principle of *Relevance*, which Roberts models after Grice’s maxim (Grice, 1989). We adopt Goebel’s formulation of the Relevance constraint (Goebel, 2020: 148):

- (51) *Relevance in discourse:*
- a. An assertion A is relevant with respect to a discourse structure iff A is a partial or complete answer to the QUD of A .
 - b. A question Q is relevant with respect to a discourse structure iff at least one answer to Q is an answer to the QUD of Q .

Zooming in on the shovel sentence in (47a), the tool-clause does not appear to directly follow from the preceding goal-clause. The overt discourse segment can be structured as follows:

- (52)
- a₀: What is the current state of affairs (in s^{topic})?
 - a. a₁: You still have to dig up the garden.
 - b. q₁: ...
 - c. a_n: Shovel is in the shed.

As shown in (52), a_n does not directly answer any overt question under discussion. However, the topicalized bare noun “shovel” guides discourse participants in reconstructing the missing QuD by serving as an answer to the implicit question q₁. Following the principle of relevance in (51), we determine that among the possible questions inferable from a₁, the one that can receive “shovel” as a relevant answer is q₁: “What is needed to dig up the garden?” The updated discourse structure is given below.

- (53)
- a₀: What is the current state of affairs (in s^{topic})?
 - a. a₁: You still have to dig up the garden.
 - b. q₁: What do I need for that?
 - c. a₂: You need a shovel.
 - d. q₂: ...
 - e. a₃: Shovel is in the shed.

Similarly, we derive q₂: “Where can I find a shovel?” as the relevant sub-question in the discourse segment in (53). Once discourse participants have retrieved all implicit questions under discussion, the discourse structure of a shovel sentence takes the form shown in (54), where the topic status of *Shovel* indicates that it answers an implicit super-question, namely q₁.²⁵

- (54)
- a₀: What is the current state of affairs (in s^{topic})?
 - a. a₁: You still have to dig up the garden.
 - b. q₁: What do I need for that?
 - c. a₂: You need a shovel.

²⁵We omit a potential intermediate step between a₂ and q₂, in which the addressee’s question “Is there a shovel?” is met with a positive answer.

- d. q_2 : Where can I find a shovel?
- e. a_3 : **Shovel**^{→ q_1} is in the shed.

One obvious question is why discourse participants do not explicitly articulate each assertion and QuD. Typically, certain moves are omitted when they provide little to no new information. In this respect, we invoke the notion of informativity as formulated by Büring (2003).

- (55) *Informativity* (Büring, 2003: 517)
 Don't say known things, don't ask for known things!

According to Büring, information already established within the common ground (CG) of the participants is neither actively questioned nor explicitly stated in discourse exchanges. This principle squares well with our case, as anankastic bare nouns refer to the item stereotypically associated with achieving a particular goal. When the goal is explicitly stated, as in a_1 , the stereotypical condition allows interlocutors to easily map the corresponding ABN to it, making q_1 and a_2 uninformative and, therefore, omissible.

To summarize, we have supplemented the semantic analysis in this section with a discourse model centered on the question under discussion. We have shown that by applying relevance and informativity as guiding principles, discourse participants can bridge gaps in discourse structures like shovel sentences. These sentences, akin to biscuit conditionals, lack entailment between the antecedent goal-clause and the subsequent tool-clause, indicating that intermediate steps have been omitted and must be inferred pragmatically. In this context, the topicalized bare noun plays a crucial role, as it reveals the topic structure of the tool-clause, thereby casting a light on the right pragmatic pathway for interlocutors to follow. More specifically, the topicalized bare noun serves as the answer to an elided (uninformative) super-question under discussion, which directly follows from the assertion conveyed by the goal-clause.

3.4.1. Topicalization and information structure

This subsection has shown that topicalization is a key discourse strategy, as it creates a dedicated slot for the bare noun, allowing it to function as connective tissue in the QuD resolution. Nevertheless, in our compositional analysis, we have assumed a low, vP-internal position for the bare noun at Logical Form. Here, we explore an alternative approach, considering the possibility that the bare noun is composed in a higher position following topicalization/ A' -movement to [spec,CP]. We evaluate this option from both a purely theoretical and an information structural perspective.

First of all, recall that anankastic bare nouns must occur in a sentence-initial position, irrespective of their syntactic category. Example (17), repeated below as (56), illustrates this point.

- (56) Context: *Du musst noch den Garten umgraben.* ('you still need to dig up the garden')
 a. Schaufel findest du im Schuppen.
 shovel find 2SG.NOM in.DEF.DAT

- b. #Im Schuppen findest du Schaufel.
 in.DEF.DAT shed find 2SG.NOM shovel
 Intended: ‘You’ll find a/the shovel in the shed.’)

Object NPs in sentence-initial position, as in (56), without a resumptive pronoun in the middle field, have traditionally been analyzed as undergoing movement to [spec,CP] in German (see, e.g., Grohmann 2000).²⁶ By extension, we treat both object and subject ABNs as surfacing in the left periphery at syntactic level.

At LF, a movement analysis yields two possible semantic configurations, depending on whether the topical NP is reconstructed in its base position or interpreted in its surface position. These configurations are schematically illustrated below (omitting conversational backgrounds and other superfluous details). Our focus here is on the indexing options for the situation variables.

- (57) a. *Topicalization:*
 [*CP* [*NP* [FOR $\boxed{da_7/\#0}$] [λs_2 [*N'* Schaufel $\boxed{s_2/\#0}$]]]] [λe_9 [*s^{topic}* [λs_0 [...
 [*vP* *e*₉ [*VP* im-Schuppen-steh- *s*_{0/#2}]]]]]]]
 b. *Reconstruction:*
 [*CP* [*s^{topic}* [λs_0 [... [*vP* [*NP* [FOR $\boxed{da_7/0}$] [λs_2 [*N'* Schaufel $\boxed{s_2/0}$]]]]]] [*VP*
 im-Schuppen-steh- *s*_{0/#2}]]]]]]]

As shown in (57), the anankastic NP may be interpreted *de Re* when reconstructed in a vP-internal position (see (57b)). This is illustrated by the fact that in this configuration the NP scopes below the topic situation, thus allowing co-indexing with the λ -binder λs_0 . This option, however, is ruled out for the topicalized NP in (57a). Here, the bare noun outscopes the topic situation, permitting only a *de Dicto* interpretation of *Schaufel* as well as for a free variable construal for the proform *da₇*.

If we were to allow the situation pronouns within the reconstructed NP to be co-indexed with the topic situation—as permitted by the LF in (57b)—the system would incorrectly generate unattested interpretations. First, as emphasized in this paper, the bare noun cannot be evaluated with respect to the topic situation. Doing so would require the presuppositions of existence and uniqueness to apply to the topic situation, contradicting our empirical findings on number neutrality. Second, if the proform *da* were bound, the crucial link between the goal-clause and the tool-clause would be severed, yielding an implausible interpretation—one in which a shovel is typically used in yard situations where a father talks to his son.

Based on this theoretical argument, we consider option (57a) to be the most well-founded. Therefore, we assume that anankastic bare nouns are interpreted in their structurally high surface position.²⁷

Additional support for this analysis comes from the discourse functions typically asso-

²⁶Syntactic evidence for reconstruction in a lower position comes from Condition C effects and island sensitivity. See Grohmann 2000 for details.

²⁷We do not provide a full compositional analysis of (57a), as it yields the same outcome as the one illustrated in subsection 3.3 for the reconstructed position, aside from additional steps related to λ -abstraction of the moved NP, which do not affect meaning.

ciated with fronting constructions. In this regard, the use of topicalization to maintain discourse continuity is well established (cf. Frey (2005); Prince (1998)) and aligns with our claim that the topicalized ABN serves as a mediating element, facilitating discourse processing from the goal-clause to the tool-clause.

Interestingly, topicalization (TOP) is commonly distinguished from left-dislocation constructions involving hanging topics (HTLD), which generally function as discourse-breakers (Frey, 2005: 218). Under this view, ABNs are predicted to be acceptable in topicalization structures but not in hanging topic left-dislocations—a prediction that is indeed borne out.

- (58) Context: You still need to dig up the garden.
 a. Schaufel steht im Schuppen. (TOP)
 b. #Schaufel, sie_[3SG.NOM] steht im Schuppen. (HTLD)

In summary, this section has developed a multi-layered analysis of shovel sentences that accounts for the restrictions observed with anankastic bare nouns. From a formal semantic perspective, ABNs denote entities that are unique in teleological situations where a backgrounded goal is typically achieved according to the addressee’s effective preferences. From a discourse perspective, ABNs serve as the glue between the goal- and tool-clause by answering an implicit QuD inferred from the former.

With this proposal in place, in the next section we examine how it accounts for some of the empirical puzzles outlined in section 2 and explore its broader theoretical implications.

4. Empirical puzzles and plural ABNs

This section delves into the implications of our proposal, particularly with reference to the properties and distributional patterns of ABNs. First, we explain two empirical puzzles from Section 2: the absence of anaphoric uses and the restrictions on modifiers. We then take a brief look at two potential challenges posed by pragmatic competition—one involving overt (in)definites and the other concerning plural bare nouns.

4.1. Absence of anaphoric uses

ABNs have been shown to resist anaphoric linking with an antecedent, as the example in (59) illustrates.

- (59) Du musst noch den Garten umgraben. Darum habe ich **eine neue Schaufel** gekauft. (‘You still need to dig up the garden. I’ve bought a new shovel for that.’)
 a. #Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
 shovel stands in.DEF.DAT shed
 b. Die Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
 DEF.NOM shovel stands in.DEF.DAT shed

Entities that have been previously mentioned can only be retrieved using the overt definite determiner. *Strong* determiners with anaphoric uses have been argued to carry an index that tracks their antecedent (Schwarz, 2009; Jenks, 2018; Ahn, 2019). Specifically, Schwarz (2009) has shown that the non-contracted form of the definite article in German functions as a strong determiner. In this light, the contrast in (59) can be reduced to

pragmatic competition between the unindexed ι in ABNs and the indexed determiner in strong definites. This is precisely what Jenks’s *Index!* principle aims to regulate.²⁸

(60) *Index!* (Jenks, 2018: 524) Represent and bind all possible indices.

Following (60), strong definites as in (59b) are always preferred over ABNs in anaphoric contexts, since these contexts allow for indices to be represented and bound. Crucially, the ι type-shifter in (59a), unlike the strong definite, lacks an index that can track the antecedent *Schaufel*, and is therefore ruled out.

4.2. Restriction on modifiers

Another puzzling aspect of anankastic bare nouns is their decreasing acceptability under modification by non-intersective modifiers (see (61)-(62)).

(61) Context: ‘You still have to dig up the garden.’
 a. ??Rote Schaufel steht im Schuppen.
 red shovel stands in.DEF.DAT shed
 Intended: ‘A new shovel is in the shed.’

(62) Context: *Du musst noch dein Sandwich zubereiten.* (‘You still have to make your sandwich.’)
 a. ??Leckerer Schinken steht im Kühlschrank.
 delicious.NOM ham stands in.DEF.DAT fridge.
 Intended: ‘Some tasty ham is in the fridge.’

The degradation caused by non-intersective modifiers such as “red” or “delicious” follows from the specific restriction imposed by the stereotypical ordering source g_{Norm} of the teleological modal. Arguably, in typical garden-digging situations, the shovel does not need to be *red* or, more generally, to possess any property that is irrelevant to achieving the goal at hand. The same reasoning applies to bare nouns like *delicious ham*.²⁹

Interestingly, we have observed that the acceptability of modified ABNs increases when the modifier is restrictive (see (63)-(64)).

(63) Context (62):
 a. Veganer Schinken steht im Kühlschrank.
 vegan.NOM ham stands in.DEF.DAT fridge
 Intended: ‘Some/the vegan ham is in the fridge.’

(64) Context: *Du musst den Tisch lackieren.* (‘You have to varnish the table.’)
 a. Englischer Pinsel liegt im Malkasten.
 English.NOM brush lies in.DEF.DAT paintbox
 Intended: ‘An English brush is in the paint box.’

²⁸Jenks derives *Index!* from the more general pragmatic principle *Maximize Presupposition!* (Heim, 1991).

²⁹Another promising approach consistent with the explanation provided here is offered by Schlenker (2005)’s pragmatic principle *Minimize Restrictors!*, which imposes two constraints on modifiers of definite descriptions: referential relevance and pragmatic relevance (Schlenker, 2005: 391). Non-intersective modifiers are referentially irrelevant—and often pragmatically irrelevant—as they add information that is not essential for identifying the referent.

These exceptions are easily explained under the current analysis, given that restrictive modifiers such as *vegan* and *English* restrict the reference to a specific type of ham and brush, respectively. Recall that a second ordering source g^{Ad} selects for the addressee's effective preferences, which can be affected by dietary choices (as in the case of vegan ham) or the type of paint job (e.g., varnishing in (64), which typically requires an English paintbrush).

4.3. Competition with overt (in)definites

Type-shifting operators such as ι are generally restricted by Chierchia (1998)'s Blocking principle, stated in (65) (after Jenks 2018: 514).

- (65) *Blocking Principle:*
Don't do covertly what you can do overtly!

Following (65), type-shifting should be a last-resort strategy used only when overt compositional mechanisms are unavailable. To comply with this principle, languages that do not overtly mark uniqueness often do so covertly. However, this is clearly not the case for German, which marks uniqueness with an overt definite article. From this perspective, the presence of a covert type-shifter like ι in constructions that typically allow for its morphological counterpart is unexpected.

One possible explanation builds on Schwarz (2009)'s weak/strong distinction, which we have already touched upon. In German, *weak* uniqueness definites correlate with the contracted form of the definite article, while *strong* anaphoric definites correspond to the non-contracted form. This morphological distinction, however, is only visible when the article combines with a preposition; it disappears in non-prepositional NPs. Given this, one might speculate that ι -shifted bare nouns do not directly compete with definite DPs, since the latter are ambiguous between a uniqueness and an anaphoric construal.

Unfortunately, this line of reasoning faces a rather obvious hurdle. If Chierchia's Blocking Principle did not apply to NPs in German, we would expect a much broader distribution of bare nouns – contrary to empirical facts.

A more convincing alternative explanation lies in how the presupposition of inherent uniqueness is formalized. Recall that this condition is imposed by the teleological modal *FOR*. When the bare noun is first “modalized”, it denotes an inherently unique entity in the relevant situations. At a later compositional stage, the anankastic bare NP merges with ι , not to enforce uniqueness but merely to resolve a potential type mismatch in its composition with the VP. By the same token, the lack of competition between the two instances of ι can be justified based on their differing argument structures. If we follow Schwarz (2012) in assuming that in NPs only (overt) strong determiners introduce situation arguments – possibly identifying the topic situation – then the covert ι is not expected to be blocked, given its simpler argument structure. Put differently, overt iotas do not require covert modal operators, as they function as situation-restrictors themselves. In contrast, bare NPs cannot be situationally restricted by covert iotas alone. This view is supported by the interpretation of overt DPs: in the teleological contexts discussed so far, the DP-subject in *Die Schaufel steht im Schuppen* ('The shovel is in the shed.') most saliently refers to a specific shovel in the topic situation.

Again these observations square well with a theory whereby situational uniqueness always requires overt D-realization, while inherent uniqueness can be expressed covertly. Independent support for this theory comes from the interpretation of *all* NPs, for which universal quantification cannot be situationally restricted when the *all* NP occurs bare (Partee 1995; Brisson 1998, as discussed in Matthewson 2001).

- (66) a. All the girls went to the gym.
 b. *All girls went to the gym (Brisson, 1998: 7)

In (66), the quantificational domain of the *all* bare NP *all girls* cannot be restricted to the topic situation, hence the ungrammaticality. In this case, the overt definite is required. Nonetheless, *all* bare NPs are felicitous when they yield a generic interpretation, as given in (67).

- (67) All desks are brown. (Partee 1995: 583)

Given the close affinity between inherent uniqueness and genericity (cf. Šimík 2021: 381), we take these facts to constitute an additional argument in favour of the theory presented here.

The intended takeaway from this brief discussion is that while the Blocking Principle generally prevents ι from type-shifting bare nouns, it cannot do so when the inserted ι does not impose any uniqueness or situation restriction. This “weakened” ι does not compete with a uniqueness article in the first place.³⁰

4.4. Competition with bare plurals

So far we have limited our investigation to bare singulars. This choice was primarily dictated by the exceptional nature of article drop with singular count nouns. In contrast, bare plurals can appear in both predicate and argument positions in Germanic languages (Chierchia, 1998), where they usually yield existential or generic readings (Carlson, 1977; Dayal, 1999; Krifka, 2004).³¹

However, the reader will have noticed that the current proposal is not specific to bare singulars. In fact, the same observations can be extended to bare plurals as well. If the teleological scenario involves goals or tasks that are typically accomplished with multiple items, we expect bare plurals to give rise to an interpretation similar to that derived for bare singulars. This appears to be correct, as shown in (68).

- (68) Du musst noch die Hecke stutzen. (Die) Handschuhe sind
 2SG.NOM must still DEF.ACC hedge trim DEF.NOM.PL gloves are
 in Schuppen.
 in.DEF.DAT shed
 ‘You still need to trim the hedge. The gloves are in the shed.’

³⁰We return to the analogy with weak definites in subsection 5.

³¹Accounts of the two possible interpretations differ in their explanation of the ambiguity. Some scholars argue that all bare plurals refer to kinds (Carlson, 1977; Chierchia, 1998), with existential readings being attributed to the episodic nature of the main predicate. Others, however, posit a systematic ambiguity at the NP level (Wilkinson, 1991; Gerstner-Link and Krifka, 1993).

Now consider the scenario in (69) where the task is assigned to a plural number of addressees.

- (69) Context: A father standing in the yard turns to his two kids:
- a. Ihr musst noch den Garten umgraben.
2PL must still DEF.ACC garden dig.up
(‘You guys still need to dig up the garden.’)
 - b. ?Schaufel steht im Schuppen. (Bare SG)
↪ There is only one shovel in the shed.
 - c. Schaufeln stehen im Schuppen. (Bare PL)
↪ There are at least two shovels in the shed.

In the context in (69), the task is intended for two people. The bare singular in (69b) is odd, as it strongly imply that there is only one shovel in the shed, forcing the two kids to take turns. This is unexpected given our semantic analysis: since the uniqueness presupposition applies only to the teleological situations, no constraint is imposed on the number of entities in the topic situation. This is indeed how the number neutrality of ABNs was explained. By contrast, the bare plural in (69c) is fully acceptable, as it implies that the shed contains at least two shovels, allowing each child to use one.

One key distinction in multi-addressee contexts, compared to previous examples, is that they may introduce goals that require multiple tools for effective completion. In this scenario, for the two agents to efficiently dig up the garden in stereotypical situations, they should each have a shovel. As noted earlier, this optimality condition is contributed by the teleological ordering source g',Ad , which incorporates the addressees’ effective preferences.

At this point, a note on number interpretation is in order. Following much of the previous literature, we assume that singular bare nouns refer to singular/atomic individuals, while plural bare nouns denote pluralities in the inclusive sense (i.e., including both atomic and plural individuals, cf. Farkas and de Swart 2010; Krifka 1989; Lasersohn 1995; Sauerland et al. 2005, among others). Going back to the contrast in (69), the singular bare noun in (69b) appears to lead to a logical conundrum: the teleological ordering source g',Ad requires the shovels to be distributed among the two addressees (suggesting that at least two shovels are available), yet the number morphology only allows for a single shovel. This results in an odd interpretation—suggesting that the two children efficiently complete the task in a manner that is, paradoxically, inefficient (i.e., by taking turns with a single shovel). To resolve this clash, discourse participants infer that there is only one shovel available in the topic situation, which forces the addressees to accept a less effective way of completing the task (but the most effective way under circumstances).

The bare plural in (69c), by contrast, does not suffer from this contradiction. Here, the requirements imposed by the ordering source (at least two shovels) align with those of plural morphology (at least one shovel). By combining these constraints, the result is a topic situation containing at least two shovels.

Crucially, the number restrictions we have derived do not stem from a direct competition between bare singulars and bare plurals, but rather from pragmatic reasoning—shaped by conversational backgrounds on one hand and number morphology on the other. Since conversational backgrounds are context-dependent, we do not expect bare singulars to

impose singular number restrictions in all contexts. As we have observed, number neutral interpretations are generally available: consider once more a single-addressee teleological context, in which a father asks his son to dig up the garden. In this case, the use of the bare singular does not imply that there is only one shovel in the topic situation. Why? Because there is no clash between the ordering source g^{Ad} and the ABN's number morphology—both point to the existence of a singular entity as the most effective means to accomplish the goal. As a result, the actual number of available shovels in the topic situation becomes irrelevant, as long as there is at least one.³²

5. Beyond a strong-weak distinction and the cross-linguistic picture

This section takes our investigation a step further, looking at its bigger-picture implications for a theory of definiteness – especially in light of Schwarz's influential work on the weak-strong distinction in German. Broadening the scope, we also take a cross-linguistic perspective on the current proposal, exploring whether its key insights can be generalized and applied to languages with different determiner systems.

5.1. Anankastic bare nouns as weak definites?

In the end of section 2, we observed that from an empirical standpoint anankastic bare nouns do not appear to align with either strong (i.e., anaphoric) or weak (i.e., unique) definites. Departing from Schwarz (2009)'s theory, we drew from Šimík (2021)'s notion of inherent uniqueness to capture the type of uniqueness involved in these constructions. Since Schwarz's theory is specifically tailored to the determiner system in German (and Fering, cf. Ebert (1971)), this choice merits closer scrutiny.

Briefly, Schwarz (2009) argues that weak determiners lexicalize ι , while strong ones additionally carry an index-argument tracking an antecedent referent. The contrast is illustrated below. While the contrast becomes only visible in standard German when the weak definite can contract in prepositional phrases, many varieties of West-Germanic languages morphologically distinguish between the two determiners, as Fering below illustrates (Ebert, 1971)83.

- (70) a. A hünj hee tuswark.
 DEF.WK dog has toothache
 'The dog has a toothache.'
 PSP: there's a unique dog in the given topic situation.
- b. Di hünj hee tuswark.
 DEF.SNG dog has toothache
 'The dog has a toothache.'
 PSP: the dog has been previously mentioned in the discourse.

As the presuppositions in (70a)-(70b) show, contextual uniqueness of the referent depicted by the NP licenses the weak definite in (70a), without the entity having to be active in the discourse. The latter is however a necessary condition for licensing the strong definite in (70b).

Cross-linguistic support for a weak-strong distinction comes from languages like Akan

³²The same reasoning accounts for the use of a bare plural in (68). As expected, the bare singular would be quite odd in this context.

(Arkoh and Matthewson, 2013), Bangla (Biswas, 2014) and Mandarin Chinese (Jenks, 2018) (but see Dayal and Jiang (2023); Owusu (2022)), which lack (obligatory) articles. Studies on these languages suggest that weak definites align with bare nouns to some extent, although their uses represent only a subset of the meanings associated with bare NPs.³³

Given this, a natural hypothesis is that bare nouns in German correspond to weak definites. Since weak definites carry less semantic content than their strong counterparts, it would make conceptual sense for article omission to yield weak-like interpretations—particularly given that standard German does not morphologically distinguish between the two forms in argument position.

Some initial support for this view comes from the fact that weak definites, just like anankastic bare nouns, generally disallow anaphoric linking.

- (71) Hans hat einen Schriftsteller und **einen Politiker** interviewt. Er hat
 Hans has INDF.ACC writer and INDF.ACC politician interviewed he has
#vom / **von dem** **Politiker** keine interessanten
 from.DEF.WK.DAT from DEF.SNG.DAT politician no interesting
 Antworten bekommen.
 answers received
 ‘Hans interviewed a writer and a politician. He didn’t get any interesting answers
 from the politician.’ (from Schwarz 2009: 30)

More evidence for the analogy comes from intersective modifiers. We have argued these are ruled out with ABNs. Similar observations have been made for weak DPs (Carlson et al., 2006).

- (72) a. Hans listened to the radio. (weak/strong)
 b. Hans listened to the red radio. (#weak/strong)

Given the theory developed here, whereby anankastic bare nouns encode some kind of uniqueness and a bridging relation with the antecedent clause, it is tempting to trace a parallel with weak definites, as these contribute ι type-shifting and exhibit bridging relations. However, weak definites are only licensed in bridging contexts denoting part-whole relations (see (73)).

- (73) **Der Kühlschrank** war so groß, dass der **Kürbis**
 DEF.NOM fridge was so big COMP DEF.NOM pumpkin
im / **in #dem Gemüsefach** untergebracht werden
 in.DEF.WK.DAT in DEF.SNG.DAT crisper stowed be
 konnte.
 could
 ‘The fridge was so big that the pumpkin could easily be stowed in the crisper.’
 (from Schwarz 2009: 52)

Crucially, these uses are attributed by Schwarz to situational uniqueness, as the weak

³³For Bangla, however, Biswas (2014) claims a one-to-one correspondence. But see Yip et al. (2023) for a different view.

definite expresses reference to the unique entity in the topic situation that bears the relevant property – in (73) “crisper” (this equally applies to the the definite NP denoting the “whole” in (73)). This notion of uniqueness is hardly compatible with Šimík’s notion of accidental uniqueness. In fact, it seems to align more closely with that of inherent uniqueness.

Schwarz further extends part-whole bridging to events, as illustrated in (74).

- (74) a. Context: How did the proposition to Mary go?
 b. Sie hat einen Kratzer am Ring entdeckt [...].
 she has INDF.ACC scratch at.DEF.WK.DAT ring discovered
 ‘She discovered a scratch on the ring.’ (adapted from Schwarz 2009: 160)

According to Schwarz, in (74), the context introduces a proposing super-event, thereby licensing the weak definite *am Ring*, based “on the general knowledge that acts of proposing (at least typically) involve a ring” (Schwarz, 2009: 160). Weak definite uses such as (74) are particularly revealing because they closely parallel anankastic instances of bare nominals: they involve bridging with a situation/event and refer to entities that are inherently unique within that (stereotypical) situation.³⁴

If this analogy is on the right track, the weak-strong distinction remains viable, with ABNs forming a sub-group within a broader class of weak definites. An alternative perspective, also advocated by Šimík (2021), suggests an ontological revision of definiteness—one that incorporates a more nuanced notion of uniqueness, contingent on the type of situations restricting the uniqueness domain. To shed some light on the uniqueness-definiteness debate, we would like to offer a brief glimpse of the cross-linguistic picture, considering a small set of languages. While this overview is by no means exhaustive, it will hopefully help assess whether ABNs are a quirk of spoken German or whether anankastic-like analyses generalize to languages with very different article paradigms.

5.2. The cross-linguistic landscape

We provide data from languages with different article paradigms and parametric settings in the sense of Chierchia (1998):³⁵ Germanic varieties that lexicalize weak determiners in argument position; an argumental language like Czech, where bare nouns can occur freely in argument position but correlate with inherently unique definites; a predicative language like Italian, where bare nouns are severely restricted and only possible when plural or mass; an argumental language like Akan that like Czech allows for bare nouns in argument position, but that unlike Czech possesses a definite article (Bombi, 2018).

First, we note that several varieties of German distinguish between weak and strong definite articles at morphological level (for a list of Germanic varieties and German dialects, see Schwarz 2009: 12). These languages provide an ideal testing ground for assessing

³⁴By the same reasoning, the weak definite in (73) can denote an inherently unique entity in the sense of Šimík. Arguably, fridges are typically equipped with a single crisper. However, part-whole bridging uses are not explicitly discussed in Šimík 2021.

³⁵Chierchia distinguishes argumental languages, where nouns are entity denoting, from predicative languages, where nouns denote properties. Nouns in argumental languages can occur bare in argument positions without any restriction. By contrast, nouns in predicative languages require a determiner to feature in argument positions.

the status of ABNs with respect to the weak-strong distinction. To this end, we present data from East-Franconian³⁶ – an Upper German dialect spoken in Franconia, that is the northern part of Bavaria. Below are three shovel sentences with three different anankastic nouns: a masculine singular noun in subject position (example (75)), a feminine singular noun in subject position (example (76)), a masculine singular noun in object position (example (77)).

- (75) Du musst noch n’Gartn umgrām. (Subj, Fem)
 (‘you still need to dig up the garden’)
 a. **Dê Schaufl** stieht in dôr Schupp. (weak)
 b. #**Die Schaufl** stieht in dôr Schupp. (strong)
 Intended: ‘A/the shovel is in the shed.’
- (76) Dēr Naxl hier muss noch nei dê Wand. (Subj, Masc)
 (‘The nail still needs to be driven into the wall.’)
 a. **Dôr Hammôr** liecht offm Kannepē. (weak)
 b. #**Der Hammôr** liecht offm Kannepē. (#strong)
 Intended: ‘A/the hammer is on the bench.’
- (77) Dēr Naxl hier muss noch nei dê Wand. (Obj, Masc)
 (‘The nail still needs to be driven into the wall.’)
 a. **In/en Hammôr** finnste im Kellôr. (weak)
 b. #**Dēn Hammôr** finnste im Kellôr. (#strong)
 Intended: ‘You’ll find a/the hammer in the basement.’

Examples (75)-(77) show a clear contrast between the two types of definites: while the weak definite is perfectly natural in the tool-clause, the strong definite is consistently rejected.³⁷

It is important to note that while the weak definite is the preferred choice for our consultants, the bare noun is also an available option in these cases. The fact that bare nouns are not ruled out in teleological contexts in languages where uniqueness is already overtly encoded suggests that weak definite DPs and bare NPs do not stand in direct competition in shovel sentences.³⁸

Next, we test the availability of anankastic uses for bare nouns in Czech. Based on the discussion in section 3.2, NP-reference in Czech seems to align with a inherent vs accidental uniqueness distinction rather than a weak-strong dichotomy. Given that our analysis of ABNs as inherently unique definites originated from Šimík (2021)’s account of Czech bare nouns, we would expect that these are felicitous in teleological contexts. This prediction is borne out.

- (78) Context: Musíš ještě zryt zahradu. (‘You still need to dig up the garden.’)
 a. **Lopata** je v kůlně.
 shovel.NOM is in shed.LOC

³⁶More specifically, from the Erzgebirgisch dialect spoken in Saxony, at the German-Czech border.

³⁷Similar judgments are obtained for Swabian, Bavarian, Thuringian and Swiss German.

³⁸This observation might indirectly support the idea that the source of the uniqueness presupposition in ABNs lies outside the covert type-shifter.

An anankastic account of bare nouns in German

- b. **?#Ta lopata** je v kůlně.
 DEM.NOM shovel.NOM is in shed.LOC
 Intended: ‘A/the shovel is in the shed.’

- (79) Context: Nezapomeň zamést podlahu. (‘Don’t forget to sweep the floor.’)
 a. **Koště** najdeš ve sklepě.
 broom.ACC find.2SG in cellar
 b. **?#To koště** najdeš ve sklepě.
 DEM.ACC broom.ACC find.2SG in cellar
 Intended: ‘You’ll find a/the broom in the cellar.’

In examples (78)-(79), the topicalized tool-denoting noun is most felicitous when bare. The use of a demonstrative determiner leads to a clear degradation of the sentence. While this is unsurprising under Šimík’s proposal, more interestingly Czech ABNs, similar to their German counterpart, exhibit number neutrality, as illustrated below.

- (80) Context: Petra keeps three brooms in her basement. Her son needs to take care of house chores this weekend, since he returned home late. She tells him:
 a. Nezapomeň zamést podlahu. **Koště** najdeš ve sklepě. (ABN)
 (‘Don’t forget to sweep the floor. A/the broom is in the basement.’)
 (81) Context: Jiří recently bought two new shovels to add to his collection. He now has six, all safely stored in the shed. Turning to his son, he says:
 a. Musíš ještě zryt zahradu. **Lopata** je v kůlně. (ABN)
 (‘You still need to dig up the garden. A/the shovel is in the shed.’)

The acceptability of sentences (80a) and (81a) in their respective contexts, which involve a plural number of individuals in the topic situations, indicates that uniqueness of the entity denoted by the ABN must be satisfied in stereotypical goal-achieving situations resembling the topic situation, rather than in the topic situation itself.

Similar effects are observed in Italian, where the anankastic NP must nevertheless be accompanied by the overt definite determiner.

- (82) Context: Devi ancora scavare il giardino. (‘you still need to dig up the garden.’)
 a. **La pala** è nel capanno.
 DEF shovel is in.DEF.DAT shed
 ~> there might be more than one shovel in the shed.
 b. **#Pala** è nel giardino.
 shovel is in.DEF.DAT shed
 Intended: ‘A/the shovel is in the shed.’
 (83) Context: Devi ancora scrivere il bigliettino di auguri. (‘You still need to write the greeting card.’)
 a. **La penna** è nel cassetto.
 DEF pen is in.DEF.DAT drawer
 ~> there might be more than one pen in the drawer.
 b. **#Penna** è nel cassetto.
 pen is in.DEF.DAT drawer

Finally, we turn to Akan (Kwa, Niger Congo), a language in which the meaning of bare nouns appears to blur standard distinctions in terms of definiteness or uniqueness, as they can exhibit both definite and indefinite interpretations and may refer to either unique or non-unique entities. This range of diverse uses has led to several competing accounts in the literature. More concretely, Akan bare nouns have been argued to be underspecified for uniqueness Arkoh and Matthewson (2013), to be ι -shifted in their indefinite uses in the sense of Dayal (2004) while denoting proper nouns in their definite uses (Bombi et al., 2019), or to denote plain indefinites (Philipp, 2023).

Despite this lack of consensus, research has shown that definite uses in Akan bare nouns are restricted, occurring primarily with inherently unique nouns – such as globally unique nouns (e.g., *sun*, *moon*), functional relational nouns or superlatives (cf. Owusu (2022: 57), Bombi et al. (2019: 190)). Notably, bare nouns in subject position usually yield definite interpretations (Philipp, 2023: 154).

Against this backdrop, we present novel data on anankastic bare nouns in Akan, which appear to align with our findings in German and may offer fresh insights into the ongoing debate on definiteness in Akan. Consider examples (84)-(85).

- (84) Context: Kofi is helping Ama on her farm. He pauses for a moment, unable to find a suitable tool to dig up the soil. Ama, knowing she has some shovels stored in the shed, tells him:
- a. Asaawa wɔ ɛdan nɔ mu. Kɔ fa bra.
 shovel COP room DEF inside go bring come
 ‘(A/the) shovel is in the shed. Go bring it.’
 One consultant’s comment: “doesn’t matter how many shovels are in the shed.”
- (85) Context: Kofi and Ama need to repair a fence that was broken by a goat. Kofi is unsure how to proceed. Ama tells him:
- a. Hama (nɔ) wɔ adaka nɔ mu.
 hammer DEF COP box DEF inside
 ‘A/the hammer is in the box.’
- b. Wo-be-hu hama (nɔ) wɔ adaka nɔ mu.
 2SG-FUT-see hammer DEF COP box DEF inside
 ‘You’ll find a/the hammer in the box.’

In examples (84)-(85), the tool-denoting noun does not require the overt definite article *nɔ*. The resulting interpretation is similar to that derived for German ABNs. Importantly, as the context in (84) clearly shows, the bare noun does not make reference to a unique entity in the topic situation. While this is expected if the bare noun receives an indefinite interpretation, it is less clear what accounts for number neutrality in subject bare nouns (especially on the basis of a proper noun analysis). Note that the definite article cannot be omitted if the context does not explicitly state the anankastic role of the noun. This is illustrated in (86)

- (86) Context: Akua has recently bought some new farming tools. But, she cannot find them anywhere. Awusi tells her:

- a. Asaawa #(nó) wɔ ɛdan nó mu.
 shovel DEF COP room DEF inside
 ‘A/the shovel is in the shed.’

As a final remark, anankastic construals with bare nouns in Akan do not appear to be limited to a structurally high position, unlike in German. This suggests that the insertion of ι type-shifters may be subject to syntactic constraints that vary across languages, influenced by language-specific factors such as the determiner system, the status of the language as argumental or predicative, and the competition that arises from them.

6. Conclusion and outlook

In this paper, we have defended an anankastic analysis of German singular count nouns that can exceptionally appear bare in goal-achieving contexts. Specifically, we have argued that anankastic bare nouns are not interpreted relative to the topic situation but rather to stereotypical teleological situations where the goal expressed in the antecedent clause is realized. This situation restriction is imposed by a covert teleological modal and yields a uniqueness interpretation for the bare noun. When topicalized, the bare noun can undergo ι -shifting into an entity, allowing for semantic composition with the rest of the clause.

Furthermore, we have shown that topicalization is a necessary condition for article drop for two key reasons. From a compositional standpoint, it reinforces a free-variable interpretation of the teleological modal, preventing binding by the topic situation. From a discourse perspective, it makes explicit the hidden QuD structure of shovel sentences, thus allowing discourse participants to link the tool-clause back to the goal-clause.

In an effort to place this proposal within the broader discussion on definiteness, we have taken a brief look at languages with different determiner systems, revealing striking parallels in how bare nominals (or weak definites) are used to convey anankastic-like interpretations. These patterns point to a more general mechanism based on situation restriction, which can reinforce uniqueness interpretations even in the absence of overt uniqueness markers.

On one hand, these findings suggest the need for a more refined view of definiteness – one that goes beyond the simple strong-weak dichotomy. This aligns with recent work questioning the universality of that classification (Yip et al., 2023; Dayal and Jiang, 2023; Owusu, 2022). On the other hand, we have argued that refining Schwarz’s theory in order to incorporate Šimík (2021)’s notion of inherent uniqueness may offer broader empirical coverage. From this perspective, ABNs can be seen as a special sub-class of weak definites that require a particular type of bridging relation.

With this in mind, we have reasons to believe that the account presented here is not limited to anankastic nominals, rather it may be extended to similar constructions where both topicality and situation restriction play a key role in licensing the omission of the article. One example is offered by sentences such as (87).

- (87) a. Komm rein! Schuhe kannst du anlassen!
 Come.IMP in shoe.PL can 2SG leave.on
 ‘Come in! You can leave the shoes on.’

- ↪ the shoes that you're wearing.
- b. Komm rein! Jacke kannst du hier aufhängen.
 Come.IMP in jacket.SG can 2SG here hang
 'Come in! You can hang the jacket here.'
 ↪ the shoes that you're wearing.

Examples like (87) involve topicalized bare nouns within modal imperative constructions, akin to several shovel sentences discussed in this paper. The bare nouns *Schuhe* ('shoes') and *Jacke* ('jacket') do not receive a standard existential or generic interpretation; instead, they express situational uniqueness through bridging ('the shoes/jacket you are wearing'), similar to anankastic bare nouns and, more broadly, weak definites. While the bridging relation in (87) is not explicitly teleological, these bare nouns appear to be evaluated with respect to stereotypical situations, much like ABNs. In this case, the typical situations involve being welcomed into someone's home, where it is customary to remove one's shoes/jacket.³⁹

Another future avenue of research may attempt a unified analysis of anankastic bare nouns with Geist (2021)'s specificational bare nouns that we touched on in section 1. An example is given in (88) (after Geist 2021).

- (88) Context: Doch in den Tagen vor der Wahl spricht fast niemand mehr über diese Träume. ('But in the days leading up to the election, almost nobody talks about these dreams anymore.')
- a. **Grund** dafür ist die Gewalt.
 reason for this is DEF.SG violence
 'The reason for this is the violence.'

Geist demonstrates that in specificational copular clauses like (88), bare nouns must be topicalized and receive a uniqueness interpretation. She argues that these bare nouns typically denote functional concepts (Löbner, 2011), which are inherently relational and unique. This inherent uniqueness renders the definite article redundant (Geist, 2021: 27).⁴⁰

Our findings align with Geist's in demonstrating a broader mechanism governing the interpretation of topicalized nouns and their ability to appear without overt determiners. We have shown that one type of bridging relation that licenses article drop is teleological. Additionally, inherent uniqueness can arise through modal operators that impose situation restriction via a stereotypical ordering source. From this perspective, Geist's account and ours can be unified, provided that inherent uniqueness may be realized either lexically (through functional concepts) or grammatically (via situation restriction). Future research should further investigate the range of bridging relations involved and explore the various ways in which inherent uniqueness is established.

³⁹A more detailed account of these sentences is left for future research.

⁴⁰More precisely, according to Geist, the definite article serves two functions: imposing uniqueness and marking case. Since functional NPs are inherently unique and are not assigned case by the copula, the article becomes unnecessary.

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